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Comparison of the effects of the integrated learning environments between the social science and the mathematics

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ABSTRACT

The integration of e-learning and active learning is expected to be effective for the improvement in the digital native students' leaning. Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) is widely used as Learning Management System (LMS) in e-learning. Video streaming is also used as one of the learning contents in e-learning.

Moodle and mediasite video contents are used in the mathematics course "Statistics for Engineers" and the social sciences course "Principles of Technology

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Management" with our university's LMS called e-Syllabus. Both courses are carried out by flipped learning and active learning.

It is expected that students' usage of e-Learning is different between the social sciences course and the mathematics course. Questionnaires about the learning effects and the validities are carried out for Mechanical Engineering students.

Both courses had video contents and good textbooks. Many students taking "Principles of Technology Management" course did preparation and review with the textbook rather than e-Learning. 60% of the students who took "Statistics for Engineers" course used Video contents.

More than half of the replies support the flipped teaching and active learning rather than the class of a lecture entity. The usefulness of the textbook was also confirmed for the digital native student.

1 INTRODUCTION

From ancient times, education has been conveying knowledge. In the ancient Confucius era, the disciples studied at word of mouth what their master said. In the Middle Ages, the learning meant reading the classical literatures. In modern ages, the textbook was invented and students wrote down on their notes the contents which a teacher wrote on a blackboard based on the textbook. The educational style in which a teacher conveyed knowledge to students has continued for a long time.

Recently, the contents which are required for education are changing. Japan's Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) focuses on developing students' active learning ability to adjust oneself to changes proactively, explore a future goal of one's own, and evaluate that goal flexibly and generally from a broad perspective [1]. The education which develops the competence to practice and apply the studied knowledge and skill is required. It is important to bring up the ability to tackle problem detection and solution. For that purpose, the effectiveness of problem-based learning and project-based learning (both abbreviated to PBL) has been accepted widely [2].

Not only the contents but also the education / learning methods are changing with progress in Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Bill Gates said "Five years from now on the Web for free you'll be able to find the best lectures in the world. It will be better than any single university." at the Techonomy conference in Lake Tahoe, CA in 2010. Although there are still many universities which give lectures in the old fashion class rooms, students' attitudes have also been changing. Mark Prensky describes "Our students have changed radically. Today's students are no longer the people our educational system was designed to teach [3-4]. "

Aiming at IoT application and realization of Society5.0, MEXT and the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI) in Japan are advancing the measure for Active Learning and EdTech. The Education Reform Committee of MEXT considered the innovation of the education corresponding to progress of technology and the high school reform corresponding to a new era. The Committee has proposed the

following to the Cabinet; aiming at collaboration learning corresponding to every person's ability and aptitude, empirical study about effective utilization of the technology like EdTech is needed by collaboration of the school, corporations, etc.

Those proposals focus on the main contents about the educational environment and the educational method corresponding to Society5.0. On the other hand, it is necessary to accumulate data on EdTech utilization suitable for the actual condition about the responses of the students who are learning by EdTech.

The authors are carrying out the classes which use e-Learning materials and textbooks in Kanazawa Institute of Technology (KIT) in Japan. Their research work on PBL was adopted by the Grant in Aid for Scientific Research in 2019.

In this paper, we firstly introduce our e-Syllabus LMS. Next, the difference of course contents between the mathematics course “Statistics for Engineers” and the social sciences course “Principles of Technology Management” will be introduced. The questionnaire survey was conducted for the student of the department of mechanical engineering. We will discuss about the questionnaire results on the integrated learning environment.

2 E-SYLLABUS SYSTEM IN KANAZAWA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

2.1 What is e-Syllabus?

Each university shows its students the syllabus which shows the contents of learning of each course. Many syllabuses show what kind of contents students study by the class of each week. However they are only shown at the time of course introduction or the first classes.

Our university launched the e-Syllabus in 2016 [5]. The teachers who take charge of their coursework are utilizing the e-Syllabus as one of communication tools with students and as the system which is useful for students' active learning.

The procedure how students access e-Syllabus is shown in *Fig. 1*. E-Syllabus will be displayed, if a student logs in to his page from the portal site, opens his list of courses and click the course. The example of an e-Syllabus image is shown in *Fig.2*. E-Syllabus displays the contents of learning of weekly classes with the guide of learning targets, scholastic evaluation method, and preferred achievement, etc. The teacher in charge can upload handouts or visual contents, and carry out tests and questionnaires in the contents area of weekly learning. Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) is widely used as Learning Management System (LMS) in e-learning. Video streaming is also used as one of the learning contents in e-learning. E-Syllabus can also carry out links with these contents.

Teachers can browse not only the e-Syllabus of their own classes but also that of other classes. Teachers can share the each other's contents of classes, and the operation method through e-Syllabus.

Fig. 1. e-Syllabus access procedure

Fig. 2. Example of e-Syllabus

2.2 Flipped learning and active learning with e-Syllabus

E-Syllabus is a powerful tool when carrying out flipped learning and active learning. The teacher uploads preparation teaching materials and movies before the class, and gives assignments. Students prepare their lessons by e-Syllabus, and participate in the class. The teacher does the quiz which confirms preparation results, receives questions from students or guides discussion by students in school hours. He can carry out quiz and questionnaires by e-Syllabus in school hours, and can confirm degree of comprehension on the scene.

3 COURSE CONTENTS

Using e-Syllabus, authors conducted the classes of Statistics for Engineers, the classes of Principles of Technology Management and the classes of Project Design. The contents and the pedagogical effects of Project Design have already been reported [6-7]. In this paper, we introduce the e-Syllabus contents of Statistics for Engineers and that of Principles of Technology Management. The lectures by teachers were the main body for these courses formerly.

3.1 Statistics for Engineers

This is an elective subject for studying statistical analysis techniques and is targeting the sophomore students of all the departments. The students who choose this course are increasing in number.

The class is carried out as a flipped classroom. There are many textbooks about statistics. In this course, while using a commercial textbook, video teaching materials and preparation assignments are distributed using e-Syllabus. With video teaching materials, the teacher explains the examples of the problems of the textbook. The

example of video contents is shown in Fig.3. In class, the teacher reviews the main contents of the text book and students solve exercise problems. The teacher explains the problem in which many students were mistaken.

Fig. 3. The example of video contents in Statistics for Engineers e-Syllabus

3.2 Principles of Technology Management

Technology management is the scheme which develops, maintains and improves products, services, and systems making full use of technology. This program was developed by Dr Ishii and Dr Nakano as a part of the liberal arts curriculum of KIT [8-10]. The program contains 11 lecture topics and is compulsory for juniors of all the departments and aims to develop ability for students to do occupation selection.

The class is also carried out as a flipped classroom using e-Syllabus. An example of e-Syllabus of one class is shown in Fig. 4. Students prepare the lesson using the original textbook and mediasite contents which are PowerPoint slides with lecture voice. The degree of comprehension in preparation is confirmed in a class using e-Syllabus quiz system and through the group discussion. The teacher explains the group work based on the lecture topic and students carry out the group work. The group work functions as the training in which the leader fixed in order exercises leadership.

Fig. 4. The example of e-Syllabus of a Principles of Technology Management class

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Evaluation by questionnaire

The usage of e-Syllabus can be measured by access log. All students accessed e-Syllabus. However the purpose of their access or usability cannot be judged by the log. Therefore, questionnaire-based evaluation was carried out in order to measure the usage of video contents and the attitude on e-learning. The questionnaire survey was conducted using e-Syllabus for the student of the department of mechanical engineering. Ten questionnaires are designed to evaluate the usability of e-learning. They are listed on *Table 1*. They are multiple-choice questions. Those who answered (e) in Q.1 skipped Q.2 through Q.7. Each question has a field for free description.

Table 1. Questionnaires on e-learning

No.	Questions	Multiple choice
1	How many e-Learning teaching materials did you use?	(a) all, (b)2/3, (c) half, (d) 1/3, (e) less
2	What is the purpose of using e-Learning materials?	(a) prep, (b) review, (c) test prep, (d) report assignment, (e) others
3	Method of video selection	(a) each chapter/problem, (b) all in one, (c) others
4	Voice speed control	(a) X 0.5-2.0, (b) more than twice, (c) others
5	Video viewability	(a) OK, (b) not good, (c) others
6	Audio contents preference	(a) with explanation, (b) without audio,
7	Free description	
8	e-Learning and textbook usage	(a) both, (b) e-Learning, (c) textbook
9	Preference of flipped learning or normal lecture	(a) flipped, (b) normal lecture, (c) others
10	How do you change after the course?	(a) very positive, (b) positive, (c) none, (d) others

4.2 Questionnaire results and discussion

29 students in 53 successful candidates answered to the questionnaire in the Statistics for Engineers (SE) class. 53 students in 54 successful candidates answered to the questionnaire in the Principles of Technology Management (PTM).

The results are shown in *Fig.5*: SE represents Statistics for Engineers and PTM for Principles of Technology Management which are shown to be compared for each

question. The result of Q1 shows 60% students of SE use e-Learning video materials and 45% students of PTM use them. As the results of Q3, Q4, Q5 and Q6 show, video and audio contents are satisfactory.

Fig. 5. Questionnaire results of Statistics for Engineers and Principles of Technology Management

SE students use them for both preparation and review, and PTM students use them mainly for preparation as shown in Q2. That is because SE video contains the solution of exercises which can be used for both, whereas PTM requires preparation for the active learning in class.

The results of Q8 show more than half of SE students use both the textbook and the e-learning material whereas most of PTM students use mainly the textbook. As both courses have the good textbooks, students can learn from the textbooks. Even with e-learning materials, textbooks are effective to digital native students. They may not need to watch videos which explain the textbook contents. However SE students watch videos which the teacher explains how to solve exercises even if the exercise answers are shown on the textbook. Video contents are helpful to study how to solve exercises.

The results of Q9 show more than half of the replies support the flipped teaching and active learning rather than the class of a lecture entity. However 23% of SE students or 38% of PTM students do not prefer the flipped learning. In affirmative free descriptions, there are opinions that the understanding deepens and the motivation for learning increases by active learning as shown by many literatures. On the other hand, some students do not prefer the flipped learning because there are many assignments for other classes and it is hard to prepare for the active learning. Especially for PTM, as there are many technical terms, some students prefer the lecture of the teacher with rich experience to the group work of students.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The e-Syllabus is used as the integrated learning environments with the textbooks in "Statistics for Engineers" course and "Principles of Technology Management" course. These courses are carried out by flipped learning and active learning. The e-Syllabus is one of communication tools with students and is useful for students' active learning.

Questionnaire-based evaluation was carried out in order to measure the usage of video contents and the attitude on e-learning. More than half of the replies support the flipped teaching and active learning with e-Syllabus rather than the class of a lecture entity. It is verified that students' usage of e-Learning is different between the social sciences course and the mathematics course.

As the further research work, it is required to add INDEX FOR TECHNICAL TERMS to the e-Syllabus and to see an attendance student's response.

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